

Review Article

Surrealist Movement

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ABSTRACT

This paper analyses the definition, its sources, merits and demerits. The French poet and critic Andre Breton founded Surrealism, a literary and artistic movement. It was a movement in painting, sculpture and literature. In this way, surrealism is a modern psychological concept that regards the subconscious □ the state of dream. Being much chaotic in subject matter it failed. Moreover, it did not match the common English taste. The rank and file could not comprehend it.

Key words: Surrealism, Freudian, consciousness, poetry and psychology

The poetry of the 20th century was characterized by traditional as well as experimental poetry. Traditional poetry roughly includes the Edwardian, Georgian, War poetry and so on. It was based on pastoral or homespun themes and followed a combined trend of the romantics and neo-classicists. Experimental poetry includes Imagist poetry; Neo-Metaphysical Poetry, Surrealist Movement and Neo-Romanticism.

Surrealism is a literary and artistic movement founded by the French poet and critic Andre Breton. Breton published his Surrealist Manifesto in Paris in 1924 and held the view that the irrational is the best mode of perceiving and representing reality. Surrealism emphasized the role of the unconscious in creative activity and employed the psychic unconscious in a more orderly and more serious manner. It was a movement in painting, sculpture and literature. Surrealists stressed hallucination, psychotic utterance, automatic writing and free associations.¹

Surrealism, as defined by Breton, is dedicated to revising our definition of reality. It includes automating writing, accounts of dreams, trance, narration, poems and paintings created as a result of random influences, art which pictured images of paradox and dream, were all devised to serve the same fundamental purpose to change our perception of the world and hence to change the world itself. By dint of automation they were to write whatever words came into their conscious mind. These words were regarded as inviolable. It was believed that this free flow of thought would establish a rapport with the subconscious mind of the readers.

The surrealist fascination with eroticism was largely a product of Freudian influence. After all, Freud's assertion of the central role of sexuality in human affairs could itself be seen as a direct challenge to the rationalist assumption of the previous centuries. Firmly rooted in the subconscious, sexuality acquired a validation which made it a major weapon in the surrealist armoury. The surrealists make effort to express whatever passes in the subconscious, or even the unconscious, without any control or selection by the conscious; for the surrealists, the conditions of life can and must be changed. But this transformation must never be limited to the details of sociological and psychological reality. The word 'Surrealism' was defined as a kind of automatism, by which it is intended to express verbally, in writing or by other means, the real process of thought. Thought is dictation in the absence of all the control exercised by the reason and outside all aesthetic or moral preoccupation. In the Poetry of Dylan

Thomas, there is surrealist influence. So his verse has always been mainly related to direct and indirect sex-influences in love, growth and religion.

For the surrealist, art is not a simple social co-relative or a strategy for evading an insistent reality. It is the means of provoking a fundamental revolution of the consciousness. As Aragox explains:

The vice named surrealism is the immoderate and impassioned use of stupefying image, or rather of the uncontrolled provocation of the image for its own sake and for the element of unpredictable perturbation and of metamorphosis which it introduces into the domain of representation, for each image on each occasion forces you to revise the entire universe.²

“Surrealism tries to express what is hidden in the mind by showing objects and events as seen in dreams etc.”³ In this way, surrealism is a modern psychological concept that regards the subconscious □ the state of dream. This delirium or even madness is more real than the conscious. The declared aim of the surrealist poets was a revolution against all restraints on the free functioning of the human mind including the logical reason, standard morality, social and artistic conventions and the control of artistic creation by fore thought and intention. Surrealism is not simply the striking image, the irrational phrase or the dream like texture. It is concerned with liberating the imagination and with expanding the definition of reality. It is not concerned with presenting the coherent rationality of irrationality which is found in Kafka.

Surrealism has the use of fantastic jokes, chance events as illumination, repudiation of rational processes, insistence on the inwardness of truth, concern with fundamental problems of existence, use of humour as a dialectical statement of truth.

In English literature, influence of surrealism can be found in Dylan Thomas, Henry Miller and Thomas Pynchon. M.H. Abrams also says:

The influence, direct or indirect, of surrealist innovation can be found in many modern writers in prose and verse who have broken with conventional modes of artistic organization to experiment with free association, violated syntax, non-logical and non-chronological order, dreamlike and nightmarish sequences and juxtaposition of bizarre, shocking, or seemingly unrelated images.⁴

The main fault of surrealism was that it banished from poetry all elements of mind but the one least capable of communication. In deriving against the intellectual privacy of the poets of the school of wit, it substituted an emotional privacy of even more enigmatical nature. Purely psychic automatism was with flaw. It was modified later by the conscious use of symbols derived from Freudian psychology. The meaning of surrealist art is often a secret known only to the artist's psychiatrist. The surrealist movement failed to make any progress as it was too chaotic in subject matter and far from the common English taste.

REFERENCE

¹Literary Terms in Poetry ed. A.J. Sebastian and N.D.R. Chandra (Delhi : Authorspress, 2001) 216.

²Realism: The Critical Idiom ed., John D. Jump Rapt (London: Methuen Co. Ltd., 1974) 77.

³Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary of Current English ed. Jonathan Crowther (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1997) 1203.

⁴A Glossary of Literary Terms ed. M.H. Abrams (Madras: Macmillan India Ltd., 1989) 167-168.